

Recommended citation: Riedel, U., Simon, S., Sankowski, O., Glessmer, M. S., & Krause, D. (2017). Open Assignments in a First Year Student Project. In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 1077-1085). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698393.

OPEN ASSIGNMENTS IN A FIRST YEAR STUDENT PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Many universities offer projects to support students at the beginning of their studies in order to sustainably enhance the students' motivation or facilitate orientation and network building at university.

We introduced a new, open project format during winter semester of 2015/16. In this project, freshmen develop products for specified target groups. After establishing a close cooperation with the local association of the blind and visually impaired, a user-centered approach for product development was used for the assignment where students developed a new product to simplify the daily lives of that target group. Students derived a specific technical problem statement and discussed their understanding of the problem as well as their ideas for solving them with the future users. Results of this project were an inclusive version of the popular board game

“The Settlers of Catan”, a tactile model of local main train station, and on the meta-level clear ideas for integrating this project format in the curriculum.

In this paper, we will show how different aspects of this project format can be developed, which special features need consideration when using largely ill-defined assignments, and what kind of support students need to successfully finish the project.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Attractiveness of Engineering Education, “I want to contribute to solve local problems”

Keywords: First Year Orientation, Student Project, Open Assignments

1 INTRODUCTION

Beginning their studies at university poses large challenges for many freshmen. At university they are often confronted with a number of problems: Many of them move to a new city for their studies and as a result lack personal contacts and networks. The university itself is a new environment with its own rules, and being a student planning a future career, or even just having to organize a life without daily support by parents, is a new experience. In addition, students are now responsible for their own learning progress, generally with less support than in school if difficulties arise.

Universities are increasingly interested in supporting students during this transition phase. Besides other measures already in place at Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH), we developed a first-year engineering project which started in winter semester 2012/13. This project, the Interdisciplinary Bachelor Project (IDP), is designed to motivate students for their studies and is very well received. Student teams develop for example airship propulsion systems, urban wind turbines or photo bioreactors.

To develop this project further, we introduced a new project format – using open assignments – during winter semester 2015/16, which we present in this article.

1.1 First Year Student Projects

First year student projects are widely used in universities with various objectives, e.g. to familiarize students with the campus and people at the university and to encourage them to network with each other. Some projects aim to introduce students to the general topics of their profession or to concepts of scientific practice. For engineering students, we believe that learning through their own experiences in team work and project management prepares them for their later work as engineers. Since many students enjoy or need learning by practical experiences [1], also projects that integrate practical work are in place.

Our voluntary project allows students to build identity as an engineer right at the beginning of their studies. They, as teams of ten to twelve students of all study courses, are given a challenging engineering task which needs to be solved including all steps from conceptual work to a prototype. The project is characterized by a large degree of freedom regarding the project organization and the choice of material which is very motivating and rewarding for the students. For our project, we noticed that for some students it would be even more interesting if they could pursue their own ideas, especially with respect to defining the aim of their project by themselves. We therefore adjusted our concept and included an open assignment approach.

1.2 Open Assignments

When talking about “open” assignments, we mean that students are given a problem for which they can find any solution – and any way towards that solution – they like. The problem is broadly defined, in our case “find a way to support the visually impaired and blind in a task they would like to be supported in”. We define a target group that we aim to assist, and we prescribe the solution must be “technical”, because, after all, we are training future engineers.

We chose this form of assignment for several reasons, all ultimately aiming at increasing students’ motivation for their engineering studies:

A) Experience what it will be like to be an engineer

Development of students’ professional identity takes a lot of students’ time and energy during their transition into university [2]. Many first-year engineering students wish their studies consisted of a better combination of theory and practice, not only dry theory, because in their eyes this does not relate to their future jobs as engineers [1]. By experiencing what it will be like to be an engineer, working on an authentic engineering task, a realistic view of a future professional identity is formed. This includes being confronted with others who are not interested in engineering but in something that only engineers can do: Create a technical solution.

B) Contact with professors, teaching staff, more senior students and peers

Supporting students especially during their first year of study is important because they often feel isolated and under extreme pressure [3] and wish for contact with instructors and feedback [4]. Therefore, we offer the opportunity to get in personal contact with professors, teaching staff, more senior students and peers. Additionally, working in teams and asking for help, which are a daily reality in engineering practice, is not often experienced or explicitly taught (and sometimes actively discouraged) at university which we aim to change.

C) Understand relevance of dry and/or boring subjects for their future as engineers

In order to guide students towards deep learning not only during the project but during their studies in general, it is important that they focus on wanting to master a task in order to pursue their own goals [5]. If their goal seems valuable enough, they will be willing to put in a lot of effort to reach it [6]. One important project aim is therefore that students independently identify problems and find ways to solve them, recognizing that even dry lectures teach them something useful to solve the problem at hand or problems they are likely to encounter during their future careers. This increases their motivation to attend, for example, mathematics lectures.

D) Experience competence and autonomy

Autonomy is an important motivator [7] that students typically do not experience much at university and that is therefore given in an open topic project where they not only chose the task they are working on but also how, when and where to work on it. However, being aware that failure can lead to frustration, it is important that students can succeed, which is made possible by offering mentoring and support by experts. But it is important that success is eventually attributed to students’ own efforts [8] and hence that they experience competence [7].

E) Experience meaning

Engineering is not just about building things, it is about doing something good in the world, about accepting and acting upon the social responsibility one carries as an engineer. Meaning attached to a goal, for example helping people, increases the perceived value of mastering the skills needed for that aim, therefore students are willing to invest more in gaining those skills [6].

These reasons led to the development of an “open topic” project which we will describe in the following. Section 2 describes the projects’ schedule we developed. Section 3 describes the approach used and presents the results of the project. Finally, in Section 4 we draw conclusions regarding the project.

2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The new voluntary project is offered to students of all study courses. They are supported by a team responsible for organizational aspects, a panel of experts who help on demand and tutors supporting the team processes. It has a duration of approximately one semester. The aim is to collaboratively develop a prototype of a product the user group needs. In the first run, about fifteen students took part.

The project is structured by only a few milestones in order to allow students to work largely self-determined (Fig. 1). However, in the weeks at the beginning a few workshops (e.g. basics of project management) and meetings ensure that students get all information and skills necessary to start.

Fig. 1. Project schedule of the project format “OpenTopic” (IDP: Abbreviation for “Interdisciplinary Bachelor Project”, the predecessor of the project described here)

Milestone 1 (Launch event) is an introductory meeting where students are familiarized with the ideas of the project and the people involved. Students also establish contacts to each other. A short teambuilding exercise supports them in this process. The next weeks up to the concept presentation at week 6 are used by the students to define their tasks. This involves several steps and is detailed in Section 4. At this stage, students would largely be organizing themselves with student tutors by their side, who keep the supervising team informed in case that team conflicts arise. For the supervision team, preparation of the concept presentation means to invite experts with different backgrounds such as electronics, informatics or mechanical engineering, since it is still unclear which expertise would be needed to support the students on their way.

At milestone “concept presentation”, students present their concept and their ideas for realizing a prototype. They describe their planned team structure and allocation of tasks, propose a time line and a rough estimate of the costs and discuss all those aspects with experts from different disciplines and the supervision team. With an approved concept they start into the practical project phase.

During the following weeks, the student teams work largely independently. They have team meetings and keep contact to the cooperation partner. Materials are purchased and prototypes are realized in the university's student workshop [9]. The supervision team and experts may be approached if questions arise. For example, if students decide to use 3D printing and need help, a brief introduction on CAD programming will be made possible.

Just before exam period at week 11, an interim presentation takes place to ensure that students are not overwhelmed with their tasks and lose sight of their exams. Practical results are presented at a student projects' fair at university at week 17. Depending on the progress and scheduling issues of the project partner, the final presentation of the prototypes with all people involved in the project may take place a few weeks later.

3 INTEGRATING A CONCEPT FOR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT FOR SPECIAL USER GROUPS

Corporate success depends to a large extent on the engineers and their ability to empathize with the problems and needs of the customer on one side and to design products solving them on the other side. From the product development point of view, our focus lies therefore on teaching students these abilities and giving them an impression of their future corporate work. For this task an open topic concept is a promising approach. Similar to the real circumstances, needs and requirements for the product development are largely undefined. Only the overall goal, to design an innovative product for a specific user group, is given, but all technical requirements, necessary for the product development, have to be defined by the students using their understanding of and empathy for the specific user group. To help students solving this challenging task, a user centered design approach is chosen [10].

In the project during winter semester 2015/16, the necessary contact to the special user group was made through the local association of the blind and visually impaired, so in effect we adopted a service learning approach [11]. The user centered design process conducted by the students in co-operation with the users included direct and indirect aspects: First, students were sensitized to the special needs and problems of visually impaired through their online search, a voluntary visit of a fair for assistive technology, and a simulation carried out by the members of the association of the blind and visually impaired. Here, students were asked to perform different tasks, e.g. eating with cutlery or drinking from a cup, while wearing different glasses simulating increasing degrees of visual impairment.

Direct user integration was then used for a two-staged brainstorming. In the first stage of this method the students spontaneously gathered various ideas as well as problems and needs of visually impaired people without judging the ideas. Ideas were then collected and arranged in a mind-map. It was afterwards used in the second stage of the brainstorming as basis for discussion, selection and further elaboration in a team with visually impaired users. However, the mind-map and other visualizations of ideas were only helpful for the students as a basis for their explanations. The visually impaired, on the other side, had to imagine the students' ideas without any form of supporting tools. Clusters of ideas were therefore explained and discussed in detail one by one and results documented immediately.

Apart from the brainstorming method, direct user integration was also used for the further elaboration of concepts. For this purpose students independently held contact with the members of the association of the blind and visually impaired. They mainly shared and discussed their ideas over email. Furthermore, card board models and

partial prototypes created through 3D printing were used to help understand and discuss alternative concepts during the development process as well as for evaluation of the final concepts at the end.

Of four ideas that resulted from the brainstorming, two were later realized: an inclusive version of the widely known board game, “The Settlers of Catan”, and a tactile part model of the local central station were to be designed. For the board game, board and tiles needed to be adapted which needed an elaborate exchange with the user group. Most parts were finally produced by 3D printing. Additionally, a podcast was produced comprising the rules of the game. The finished board game was handed over to the association where now members regularly meet to play the game. The group with the central station model worked out the suitable scale so that the overall model would be detailed enough for blind people and small enough to present the whole station on one large board. Staircases and escalators of the first prototype were easily recognized by the blind.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Our experiences show that an open assignment with an external partner is worth all the effort it needs in preparation and support.

In order to evaluate the project, we asked the students in an anonymous questionnaire and we had a discussion to reflect their experiences. All of them said that the simulation as well as the brainstorming session with the blind people was most valuable for them to collect ideas for useful products. Students also remarked that the openness of the assignment was very motivating for them. As one student put it: *“This project taught me personally, what I am able to achieve in respect to being creative and finding technical solutions... This fact is very inspiring and motivating for me.”* All of them wish for the opportunity to participate in more of these open projects during their time at university. Generally, they agreed that their first year project was a good start into university, especially for getting to know staff and peers. Some of them still worked voluntarily weeks after the project to produce a product better than the prototype.

Working together with visually impaired users in a user-centered design approach was a major challenge to us. The product development process is characterized by several supporting methods and tools where usually different forms of visualizations are used to show complex structures and different concept ideas as well as to support communication in between the design team. In a user-centered design approach the special user group, in our case the visually impaired people, is also part of the design team. Switching to sole verbal and written forms of communication for the brainstorming method and the whole ideation process as well as using prototypes as a mean of communication during the elaboration of the concepts, worked out quite well for us. However, in future projects with the same user group more complex product ideas may force us to adapt the means of communication and collaboration even more.

If this project should be included into the curriculum, what does it mean from the teaching perspective? We learned that several things are important when combining an open assignment with the service learning approach: First, a close cooperation with the external partner including a careful planning of the project schedule where students are introduced to the project assignment and the needs of the potential user group. Second, at university, contacts to experts of various disciplines who are committed to the project are necessary. Overall, good communication of all people involved during the time of the project is essential for good results.

Additionally, if introducing a project into the curriculum, the specific circumstances of the curricular course require a number of adaptations. For example, in 2014 the study programme for mechanical engineering at TUHH introduced a mandatory first-year project that is based on our IDP (see Section 1). Now, each winter semester nearly 400 first year students develop airship propulsion systems in teams of 10 students. Based on our experience during this transition [12], we learned that the items to be addressed include

- The learning objectives and contents of the study course
- The number of participants
- The timeline of the course and the time effort planned for the students
- The available personal resources for organizational, technical and expert support
- The materials provided or the finances provided to purchase materials
- The availability of rooms and workspaces
- The type of the exam

For all of these points, special solutions are needed. For an open topic project in a larger scale we would for example plan to engage well-trained student tutors, to introduce a project schedule with more detailed milestones, to – for the start – define a number of exchange dates with committed people from the project partner and to introduce formative assessment and reflection sessions.

In this article, we have described an open topic project for first-year engineering students. We developed a project schedule that integrates the step where students find their own project task based on the requirements of the cooperation partner. In the same way the base project was adopted as mandatory course into the mechanical engineering program at TUHH [12], we are now equipped with experiences and strategies to bring open topics into mandatory courses.

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